

VERGE: Simplifying Video Search for Novice Users

Nick Pantelidis
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
pantelidisnikos@iti.gr

Maria Pegia
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
mpegia@iti.gr

Damianos Galanopoulos
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
dgalanop@iti.gr

Konstantinos Apostolidis
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
kapost@iti.gr

Dimitris Georgalis
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
dgeorgalis@iti.gr

Klearchos Stavrothanasopoulos
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
klearchos_stav@iti.gr

Anastasia Moutzidou
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
moutzid@iti.gr

Konstantinos Gkountakos
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
gountakos@iti.gr

Ilias Gialampoukidis
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
heliasgj@iti.gr

Stefanos Vrochidis
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
stefanos@iti.gr

Vasileios Mezaris
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
bmezaris@iti.gr

Ioannis Kompatsiaris
CERTH-ITI
Thessaloniki, Greece
ikom@iti.gr

Abstract—This paper presents an updated iteration of the VERGE interactive video retrieval system. It offers various search options like free text and concept-based text search, color similarity, people and face detection, and visual and semantic similarity search. The system is designed to handle large amounts of data efficiently using advanced indexing techniques and state-of-the-art AI technology for visual content analysis. This paper describes enhancements made to improve usability for non-expert users, particularly through changes to the search and browsing interface.

Keywords—Text to Video, Multimedia Retrieval, Video Search, User Interface

I. INTRODUCTION

In the digital era, the Internet offers access to diverse media forms such as images, text, videos, and 3D graphics [1]. When viewing a scene from a favorite movie, it is not just a static image but a dynamic structure with frames/shots containing various elements like captions, timestamps, and audio. There are object and activity-based concepts, where objects are detected within a specific shot, while actions unfold across a sequence of shots. Moreover, characters and objects in these videos exist in a three-dimensional space, adding complexity.

When analyzing scenes from different sources like medical imagery [2] or footage from underwater unmanned vehicles (UUV) [3], [4], the level of complexity rises. Such images may be difficult to annotate or may have low resolution owing to the specific nature of their subjects. Therefore, managing and retrieving such diverse and intricate data remains significantly challenging due to the extensive amount of content available, inconsistent metadata, and computational complexity involved.

Apart from the various applications of video retrieval (e.g., recommendation systems, summarization), which are critical

for analysing and comprehending multimedia content, there is also a notable demand for user-friendly tools capable of smoothly integrating AI-based technologies. Specifically, this emphasis on user-friendly interfaces underscores the importance of accessibility and efficiency in multimedia retrieval systems.

There are two major annual competitions: the Video Browser Showdown (VBS) [5] and the Lifelog Search Challenge (LSC) [6], both trying to cope with these challenges. These competitions serve as platforms for evaluating different tasks via live video search sessions. In these events, participants engage in tasks related to locating specific content within video datasets, showcasing advancements in retrieval techniques and usability. Participating systems [7]–[13] employ various methods to swiftly find the correct answer. The competition comprises two parts: expert evaluation and novice user evaluation. Expert is a user with a previous knowledge of the system and how it works, while a novice user is a user that is not familiar with the system. Both users utilize the system to try to solve a number of video retrieval tasks. Therefore, in these competitions not only the performance of the systems is assessed but also the usability of each system is indirectly evaluated through the novice user sessions.

Additionally, within the CBMI conference, there is the Interactive Video Retrieval for Beginners (IVR4B)¹ special session. This session is specifically designed to emphasize novice user interactions and the usability of retrieval systems.

One notable system in this domain is VERGE as introduced in the work [14]. VERGE is a system for retrieving video content interactively. Users can perform various queries on a

¹https://cbmi2024.org/?page_id=100#IVR4B

set of images from videos through a web app, view top results, and make selections. This system had its first release back in 2012 and since then it is yearly updated alongside participation in the VBS competition.

This paper introduces a new version of VERGE with a focus on enhancing user experience for beginners through a redesigned interface.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section II offers an in-depth look at the VERGE system’s functionality and features. Then, Section III describes the new user interface comparing it with the old one. Finally, Section IV wraps up by highlighting the enhanced usability of the redesigned VERGE interface for all users.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

VERGE integrates multiple analysis methods to enhance user experience in finding specific videos easily. These include free text and concept-based text search, color similarity, people and face detection, and visual and semantic similarity.

The main analysis method of the system is the free-text video search, which calculates the similarity between complex free-text queries T with a large set of video shots V . For this purpose, the $T \times V$ network [15], a cross-modal network consisting of two key sub-networks, is utilized. Multiple cross-modal common latent spaces are built using textual and visual features and multiple textual encoders. The network is trained using a combination of four large-scale video caption datasets MSR-VTT [16], TGIF [17], ActivityNet [18] and VateX [19].

Last year, we added to our system the video semantic similarity search, where a video shot is used as a query, and our system finds the most similar video shots by comparing their cross-modal embeddings generated by the free-text video search module. This module provides comprehensive semantic information instead of only comparing visual aspects.

Another analysis method is the concept-based retrieval. It annotates the keyframes with labels from a diverse pool of over 2000 concepts, leveraging different model architectures, including ViT, EfficientNetV2, ResNet, and WideResNet. These models are pre-trained on established datasets such as ImageNet, Places365, MS COCO, and Open Images V4 as well as custom datasets, including the TRECVID SIN task and a dedicated sports dataset. For more details see Section 3.1 of [14].

Furthermore, images with similar colors can be found using the color similarity search. First, this method divides the image into 9 tiles and computes color layout descriptors based on 12 representative colors. Then, the Euclidean distances are calculated for each feature and color.

In order to find visual similar images, we utilize DCNNs for content similarity based on features extracted from GoogleNet’s final pooling layer [20]. It employs IVFADC indexing for efficient database vector storage, following the technique in [21].

People and faces detection utilizes YoloV4 [22] architecture initially trained on MS COCO [23] fine-tuned using Crowd-

Human [24] dataset for the detection of human bodies and heads.

All the aforementioned analyses can be applied individually or can be combined (except the visual and semantic similarity). In this way, users can perform a more targeted search for the scene they are looking for. The system supports the combination of only two queries. These queries can be combined either temporally or not. In particular, in the case of a temporal search, the user has to describe two scenes of the video temporally close. In the other case, both queries describe the same scene.

In the first case, both queries generate lists of shots, which are then intersected at the video level. The process retains the initial tuple from each video, maintaining chronological sequence. Afterwards, the combined list is sorted utilizing a heuristic function outlined in [14]. In the second case, the queries produce lists of shots, which are intersected at the scene level. Subsequently, the resulting list is ordered using the same heuristic function, incorporating temporal fusion.

The results of these analyses, are pre-calculated and stored in an indexed MongoDB² database. The free-text and semantic similarity search are the only ones that are performed on the fly. There is an Application Programming Interface (API) developed in Node.js³ that accesses the database and is used to perform the various queries through the User Interface (UI).

III. NEW USER INTERFACE

The VERGE system has a multiyear presence in the VBS competition. During these years, the system was changing to adapt to the needs of the competition and also incorporate the new modules that were being developed. Additionally, every year we tried to improve it in terms of user experience. However, despite our efforts, the system had ended up being too complicated for a new user. The current interface was the evolution of a redesign that happened back in 2018. Therefore, this year, with the vision to participate for the first time in the IVR4B special session of the CBMI conference, we decided to redesign the system’s user interface from scratch and completely change its workflow in order to be easier to use both for a novice and an expert user.

Figure 1 displays the old user interface. The main issue with the old UI was stemmed from how users could perform a query. First of all, in the menu all the options were visible at any time leading to user confusion. Moreover, there was no clear visual separation between the inputs for the different analyses. In order to perform a search, users had to set the value on the respective input and click the adjacent search button. Secondly, the process for conducting temporal queries was limited and not so obvious. Furthermore, a temporal query could be performed only using two free text queries or two concepts and after selecting the "temporal search/query" checkbox under the corresponding input. Often, even expert users overlooked selecting or deselecting the checkbox in order

²<https://www.mongodb.com>

³<https://nodejs.org>

Fig. 1. The old user interface that took part in VBS2024

to do a temporal search. Finally, the process of combining two queries was not intuitive. In order to combine two queries a user had to perform a query, then enable the rerank switch in the top right of the menu and perform the second query that would return the intersection of the results of this and the previous query.

The structure of the old interface is as follows. On the top of the menu, the history back button is used to perform the previous query, if there is any. Under that there is the dataset selector where the user can select the dataset in which will perform the queries. Next to the dataset selector, the query type selector can be used to select the format of the returned results. When it has the value “Default” all the keyframes that match the performed query are returned. The other option is “AVS” that returns only the first match of each video. Below these options, we have the inputs for the different types of analyses and at the bottom there is an input for submitting a text answer. The results are displayed on the right of the menu. Using the pagination buttons at the top-right corner of the application the user can navigate through the pages of the results, with each page displaying up to 500 keyframes. When the user hovers over a keyframe four buttons appear. The one in the top-left corner is used to perform a semantic similarity search that returns images with similar content to the selected one. The

button on the bottom-left corner performs a visual similarity search that returns images with similar visual information. The button on the top-right corner of the keyframe, when clicked, opens a modal window playing the keyframe’s video including options for submitting a specific time or time range of the video. Finally, the button on the bottom-right corner is used to submit the keyframe to the respective competition’s server. When the keyframe itself is clicked, a modal opens displaying all the keyframes of this keyframe’s video.

The new user interface, which is depicted in Figure 2, aims to tackle all the issues that the previous one had. The design of the menu has completely changed with a more intuitive and clean design that hides unnecessary information from the users. A novice mode is also supported, that hides more complex options from the users and adds descriptive titles to some components. On the other hand, the design of the results remains the same.

On the top of the menu, there is the logo and then the history back button and the dataset selector that have the same functionality as in the old interface. The most important part of the menu is the query containers that a user can utilize to perform a query. Each container has a descriptive title and a drop-down list with the available analyses. In the novice mode the available analyses are the free text and the

Fig. 2. The new user interface that we will use in CBMI

number of people/faces. The user can select an analysis and the corresponding input for this analysis will appear under the drop-down. By default, the free text analysis is selected. The inputs for the various analyses are the same as in the old interface except their style. The only difference is in the free text input that now supports queries in different languages utilizing the Google Translation API⁴ to translate the queries to English. When the user clicks the search button, if there is input in both query containers, a temporal search will be performed. Otherwise, it will perform a normal search. The reset button resets the query containers to their default values. On the bottom of the menu there are three buttons. The text submission button when is clicked opens a modal where the user can insert their text answer and submit it. The login button is for connecting and using the application as a user, that is necessary if you want to submit results. When activated the advanced mode button changes some elements in the interface giving more options to the user of the application. There are three main differences in the advanced mode. First of all, next to the dataset selector we have now the results format selector that its functionality is the same as the query type selector in the old interface. However, the title of the selector and the options are different. Therefore, when the option All/video is selected all the keyframe matches are returned, and when

the First/video option is selected only the first match of each video is returned. Secondly, the user can perform a normal search, a temporal one or combine the two queries and return their intersection using the corresponding additional buttons. Finally, the user can utilize two more analysis options that are not available in novice user mode, that are the concept-based text search and color similarity.

The interface is built with the Javascript library React⁵ and utilizes the API that we have developed for performing queries and communicating with the database. In general, our aim has been to create a simple and lightweight interface that does not utilize unnecessary styling and libraries that could make it slower.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents a new design of the VERGE user interface. The system includes diverse search options such as text and concept-based search, color similarity, face detection, and visual and semantic similarity search. The redesigned user interface aims to enhance usability, especially for non-expert users, by simplifying the workflow and offering clearer visual cues to address previous usability issues. The usability of the new UI will be tested in this competition and it will be adapted accordingly based on the feedback that we will get.

⁴<https://cloud.google.com/translate>

⁵<https://react.dev>

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